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A user guide to engage citizens in the Valencia Climate Alliance

Local Climate Strategies: Insights from Social Sciences & Experiences of European Cities

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Executive summary

Valencia has designed an action plan to achieve the ambitious goal of net-zero emissions by 2030. Like other cities engaged in the climate transition, Valencia needs support from other levels of government, businesses, academia, and citizens. Acknowledging the need for socially just transitions and challenges in engaging with citizens for co-creation of local climate action initiatives, this guide shares lessons learned from European cities and social science research to engage citizens in planning and implementing far-reaching climate strategies. This guide adopts a 5-steps approach to engage citizens with climate targets: discovery, entry, climate targets, implementation, and monitoring. The examples of participation initiatives from European cities and Valencia show the importance of considering the diversity of citizens' motivations, backgrounds and trust requirements.

Resumen ejecutivo (en español)

Valencia ha diseñado un plan de acción climático para alcanzar el ambicioso objetivo de emisiones netas cero en el año 2030. Al igual que otras ciudades comprometidas con la transición climática, Valencia necesita el apoyo de otros niveles de gobierno, empresas, instituciones académicas y de la ciudadanía. Reconociendo la necesidad de transiciones socialmente justas y los retos que plantea la participación de la población en la creación conjunta de iniciativas locales de acción por el clima, esta guía retoma lecciones aprendidas de ciudades europeas y de la investigación en ciencias sociales para una participación ciudadana más efectiva. La guía adopta un enfoque de 5 fases para hacer a la ciudadanía copartícipe en las metas climáticas. Las fases son: descubrimiento, entrada, definición de objetivos, implementación y seguimiento. Los ejemplos de iniciativas de participación ciudadana de ciudades europeas y de la Comunidad Valenciana muestran la importancia de considerar la diversidad de motivaciones, los diferentes contextos socio-culturales, así como la trascendencia de construir confianza con la ciudadanía con procesos de largo alcance.

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Workshop with Valencia and eight European cities' representatives, 2024

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Introduction

Citizens are critical for the success of climate action programs. That is why citizens are among the key actors in the multi-actor collaboration framework of the Valencia Mission Alliance together with the civil society, private sector, public sector, academia and mass media. When given the opportunity to engage, their local knowledge and their experiences can inform policy and foster local sustainability efforts. This citizen user guide is a tool for the Municipality of Valencia to support citizen engagement by drawing from social sciences and other experiences from different European cities, all of which are part of the EU mission of Net Zero Cities.

Methods of data collection

Five researchers hailing from social and natural sciences collaborated to write this interdisciplinary guide, through data collection, analysis, and synthesis. Their approach encompassed an array of sources, including scientific literature on citizen engagement in Europe, local reports and plans related to climate action in Valencia (Municipality of Valencia, 2023), as well as interviews with three institutions actively involved with citizens. Data was also collected in a transdisciplinary manner during a two-day workshop with eight European cities in April 2024 in the city of Valencia.

These materials provide insights and learning from existing climate initiatives in Valencia and cities in Spain and Europe. They are synthesised as recommendations to strengthen citizen engagement and examples of successful initiatives.

Content

The citizen user guide follows five steps, drawing inspiration from the preexisting ambassador user guide developed for Valencia: 1- discovery; 2- entry & introduction; 3- commitments & climate targets; 4- implementation & collaboration; 5- monitoring & reporting (Rojas et al., 2023). Each step gathers recommendations and examples from European cities.

Figure 1. Citizen user guide steps.

1. Discovery

Goal: Citizens discover the mission and the alliance, and recognize the relevance of climate action.

Why is Valencia trying to decarbonize by 2030?

With the Paris Agreement, the world has agreed to pursue efforts to limit global warming to 1.5°C, accounting for equity considerations across countries. As global warming is already hitting 1.2°C, scientists showed that reaching this goal implies reaching net-zero CO₂ emissions around 2050 globally (IPCC, 2023).

Acknowledging their greater contribution to current global warming, and their greater wealth and capabilities in reducing emissions, many developed countries from the Global North, including the ones from the European Union, are aiming at net-zero emissions (not only CO₂) in 2050, sometimes sooner.

To contribute to these goals, Spain is targeting a reduction of its emissions by 32% between 1990 and 2030 (Spanish Government, 2023). However, recent scientific studies have found this objective to be insufficient, and only aligned with limiting global warming to 2°C to 3°C (Robiou du Pont et al., 2018).

The objective of the city of Valencia, to reduce its emissions by 84% and seek to compensate for the remaining 16% in 2030, appears much ahead of the insufficient national goal (Municipality of Valencia, 2023). With this objective, Valencia sets an ambitious target, significantly contributing to a fair share of the global decarbonisation effort, and situates itself as a frontrunner city in Europe, holding the label for EU Mission for Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities.

Why are citizens needed to decarbonise Valencia?

As a developed city of about 800,000 citizens with an urban lifestyle, Valencia has great potential to invent and deploy decarbonisation plans. To this end, the city has developed an ambitious emissions reduction plan under the Valencia Climate City Contract (Municipality of Valencia, 2023). The investments needed to realise the city's plan are significant but have a high return, with about 85% of the costs being compensated by 2050. In addition, the plan would avoid costly climate impacts for generations to come. Beyond decarbonisation needs, the climate objective offers the opportunity to choose how to develop the city. The active involvement of citizens, along with other actors, is essential to ensure that the plan meets their needs, and that the transition is socially just.

As a local government bound by national legislative policies, the Municipality of Valencia has limited financial resources and regulatory power to implement its plan (Schwanitz et al., 2023). In its Climate City Contract, the Government of Valencia estimated that it could only fund 7% of the investments needed to achieve its goals (Municipality of Valencia, 2023). Great cooperation is thus essential from a broad range of actors, and citizens are required in order to demonstrate popular support for such measures and investment to the city, to the national level and to other actors needed to achieve the city plan.

Valencia's government can play a key role in informing the different actors of possible scenarios forward, reviewing the key criteria of citizens to make a just transition, and synergising the actions of local actors.

Box 1. Spaces for Encounter

The organisation Democratic Society emphasises the importance of spaces of encounter, which are informal, spontaneous meeting spaces where people can come together, converse, and informally exchange ideas. These gathering places can serve as forums for discussing issues of shared concern, such as climate change, which can help engage and empower citizens (Net Zero Cities, 2024). The design of urban infrastructure plays a crucial role in enabling or hindering the creation of these valuable spaces.

Net Zero Cities, 2024

Recommendations to operationalize this phase based on the review of Valencia's Climate City Contract, Climate Mission Alliance 2030 and the two-day workshop held in Valencia:

- **Collaborate from the beginning** with neighbourhood-level associations and entities that are on the field to reach out to people and identify their needs.
- Develop messages that connect climate change-related arguments to the **challenges and aspirations of Valencia's neighbourhoods and existing organised groups.**
- Use **narratives** to depict climate change. They should capture **multiple scales** (local and global) **and actors** (citizens, CEOs, etc.)
- Use **playful elements.** Fun games showing the causes and consequences of climate change can be better incentives for action than focusing on catastrophic scenarios and fear. As an example, the Climate Fresque¹, a game originated in France, has reached over a million people thanks to 7000 trainers.
- Make **use of the available spaces for encounters** in the city to spread the mission and promote conversations about it. Additionally, creating new spaces for encounters could further strengthen the potential.

¹ Climate Fresque: <https://highfidelitycollective.com/portfolio/team-building-pure-climate-fresque/>

Figure 2. Schematic description of the multi-level influence of citizens and cities on climate action. Several levels of government can, and have the responsibility, to regulate citizens and their emissions to provide a fair contribution to the world’s climate goals.

2. Entry and introduction

Goal: Citizens join the Climate Agreement and become members of the Alliance

Mechanisms for Citizens' Engagement in Climate Change Action

Sustained and inclusive citizen engagement is challenging. Several structural, contextual or individual barriers can prevent meaningful engagement of citizens for local climate action. However, there is enormous potential waiting to be realised. In Spain, according to a recent study conducted by the European Investment Bank, over 80% of the Spanish population is concerned about climate change impacting their daily lives and shares a desire for stricter measures. Some citizen suggestions included the replacement of short-haul flights with trains and an increase in taxes on high-carbon products (EIB., 2021). Interestingly, lower-income groups were in favour of a high carbon tax as well, however, this should be approached with caution so that policies do not impact those that are already vulnerable. For instance, another study found that Spanish stakeholders were concerned that the burden of a tax increase on fuel would affect rural and middle-income households in Spain the most (Tomas et al., 2023). However, offsetting schemes could aid payments to those households identified as the hardest-hit.

At the local level, residents of Valencia have identified cleanliness, traffic, and safety as their primary concerns, according to the latest municipal barometer of citizen opinion conducted in December 2023 and January 2024. The survey also reveals that Valencians highly value the Albufera Park and appreciate the city's network of bike lanes. Both the protection and enhancement of nature, as well as the promotion of non-motorized transport, can be directly connected to the city's climate change strategy (Levante 2024).

The motivation-capacity-ownership (MCO) framework (Mees, 2022) analyses citizen-led initiatives for climate action based on three categories that consist of motivation, capacity and ownership. Citizens' motivation for engaging depends on the expected return on investment, perceived salience/risk, and group identification. Their capacity to engage depends on their level of income, education, and perceived sufficiency of resources. Lastly, citizen's ownership is an essential pillar of engagement and depends on several factors such as peer influence, sense of own responsibility, trust in government, sense of government responsibility, environmental values and ethical concerns (Mees, 2022).

Figure 3. Motivation-Capacity-Ownership (MCO) Framework (Mees, 2022).

First, citizens' individual motivation is influenced by the expected return on investment, perceived salience/risk, and group identification. In Valencia, for example, citizens are more driven by individual and neighbourhood benefits than global climate impacts. These individual and neighbourhood benefits include decreasing energy expenses, improving the city's appearance, supporting agricultural activities, etc. On the contrary, climate change perception does not seem to be a key driver for citizens' engagement in Valencia, according to interviews and a past study (Santamarina Campos, 2009).

Second, the capacity to act includes objective capacity (resources, level of income, and education) and subjective capacity (perceived sufficiency of resources and ability to make a difference). Relying on intermediary agencies can help better understand people and build their capacities. In Valencia, retired people are overrepresented in citizen engagement processes (Personal Communication through Interviews) and can contribute to fostering citizen engagement, but other citizens' interests also need to be represented to ensure an inclusive net-zero transition with representation of diverse social groups (Fogg-Rogers et al., 2024).

Lastly, the feeling of ownership depends on factors such as peer influence, a sense of responsibility, and environmental values. The sense of responsibility may be influenced by trust in institutions and the satisfaction with government responsibility to address climate change. In Valencia, past initiatives like the GrowGreen project² and the Castellar energy community³ intended to strengthen the local associational network. Relying on existing entrusted associations can be critical as citizens were reluctant to engage with the municipality. Barriers were overcome thanks to long-term processes and personal relationships, although these strategies might be difficult to replicate at scale.

Box 2. An example of a personalised communication campaign in Valencia

In its energy efficiency promotion campaign, Valencia showcased real-life examples. Posters were deployed throughout the whole city (see picture), explaining how Sara, an employee of the municipal Energy Office, supported Rafa to save 400€ per year on his electricity bills. During and after the campaign, several citizens called the Energy Offices asking directly for Sara's advice on energy savings, evidencing the success of this personalised campaign.

2 GrowGreen Project: <https://growgreenproject.eu/city-actions/valencia/>

3 <https://energy-cities.eu/how-to-make-sure-energy-communities-thrive-in-your-city/>

Box 3. The example of the first energy community in Valencia: Castellar Energy Community

The first energy community in Valencia started in 2019, in Castellar, a semi-urban area. It serves as a showcase for others: around 6 or 7 communities are currently in the process of replicating this first experience. The energy community started after a few meetings and training (4 or 5) organised by the Fundacion València Clima i Energia, linked to the municipality. About 100 people attended these first training sessions. At the end of those first training sessions, a group of five to six people remained highly motivated, led by the president of the neighbourhood association, a retired nurse. This group of citizens eventually decided to create an association that is now the legal basis for the energy community.

After the creation of this association, Fundacion València Clima i Energia organised a larger event with the Association and all the neighbours to recruit new members for the energy community. Despite a membership fee of 600 euros and the fact that the infrastructure was not ready yet, the number of interested people quickly exceeded the number of available seats. The main motivation to join seemed to be financial, to save on current energy invoices and also future ones, in the context of energy prices instability. Another important motivation was autonomy: reduce the risk of external factors affecting energy provision and pricing (pandemic, war in Ukraine, etc). Nonetheless, the core members of the association also had the political willingness to improve their neighbourhood. Additionally, other factors such as the critical role of Fundacion València Clima i Energia in bridging the citizen association with the energy distribution company and providing assistance, citizens' trust in the president of the association, and word of mouth among the residents contributed to the success of this initiative.

Recommendations to operationalize this phase based on Motivation - Capacity - Ownership Framework and examples of mechanisms for citizen engagement in climate action are as follows:

To build citizens' motivation:

1. Consider the individual determinants of citizen engagement: highlight (non-environmental) **co-benefits** of climate action, record perceptions and opinions from non-engaged citizens to find out what motivates citizens, e.g. the cleanliness, traffic and safety.
2. In citizen engagement, construct **positive narratives** to highlight the individual or collective expected returns on investment, for example through personalised campaigns (see box 2).
3. Meet people in their **day-to-day spaces**, such as public parks and "spaces of encounter" instead of inviting citizens to an office.
4. Plan for fun activities, such as free paella, art and culture. Set a **playful tone** that facilitates interactions. Small groups can also enable community collaboration and creativity.
5. **Manage expectations** to not overpromise.
6. Collaborate with **local stakeholders**, such as existing citizens associations and local leaders/trusted people to promote group identification.

To build citizens' capacity:

1. Call on **local stakeholders** such as associations or citizen ambassadors to introduce citizens to climate transitions and build their capacities. Bridge associations with one another to build local

capacity. These social networks can cultivate group identification and shape citizens' views on returns of investment for individual and community-wide benefits.

2. **Provide municipal assistance** for enhanced citizen awareness on complex issues regarding socio-technical aspects of climate action, ie. informing citizens on legal frameworks of energy communities, or existing subsidies. Valencia's Energy Offices are a very good example of this as they provide one-stop-shops to give tailored support to citizens on a variety of issues related to energy transition and build their capacities.
3. Integrate solutions that address **vulnerabilities and needs of different groups** for socially just transitions. For instance, engaging with marginalised groups to disseminate knowledge on climate action can contribute to positive perceptions of subjective capacity (perceived sufficiency of resources and ability to make a difference). Utilise methods such as stakeholder mapping to "leave no one behind" by going beyond the usual candidates typically selected for citizen engagement.

To build citizens' ownership:

1. **Plan enough time** (years) to build citizen engagement and long-lasting initiatives. Establishing healthy decision-making dynamics is a long-term task, especially for collective action.
2. Build **trust** between citizens and Valencia Municipality through managing expectations and following through promises. Transparent monitoring and reporting processes, in which citizens are involved can help to build trust as well.
3. Highlight how local sustainability transitions are **fair and contribute to global climate action** to improve local ownership and individual sense of responsibility.

Recommendations:

- **Plan enough time** (years) to build citizen engagement
- Build **trust** between citizens and Valencia Municipality
- Highlight how local sustainability transitions are fair and contribute to **global climate action** to improve local ownership

Recommendations:

- **Bridge local associations and community groups** to build social networks and foster individual capacities
- Provide **technical assistance**, such as trainings on complex issues
- Integrate solutions that address **vulnerabilities and needs** of different groups for socially just transitions

Recommendations:

- Highlight (non-environmental) **co-benefits** of climate action
- Create and share **positive narratives**, ie. individual and collective returns on investment
- Meet people in their **day-to-day spaces**
- Set a playful tone with fun activities to motivate people
- Build reasonable expectations
- Collaborate with **local stakeholders**, such as existing citizens associations and local leaders/trusted people

Figure 4. The list of recommendations to promote citizens' motivation, capacity and ownership with the objective to foster citizen engagement with the Valencia Climate City Contract and Climate Mission Alliance

3. Commitments and Climate Targets

Goal: Citizens will determine the climate actions they will undertake to contribute to Valencia's Mission. This goal should be realised through a co-creation process that prioritises participation and deliberation.

Sub-goal: enable learnings from other mission cities.

The local climate action initiatives should not merely be based on emission reduction targets, but also include the needs of citizens for a just and inclusive transition. To create a common understanding and a sense of shared responsibility on local climate change action, participatory and deliberative processes should be utilised.

The table 1 gives some examples of tools to incorporate citizens' views when planning climate actions.

Table 1. Examples of tools to incorporate citizens' views when planning climate actions.

Main objective	Tool	Example
Brainstorm new ideas	Innovative community engagement events	In the "thought series" created in Porto, climate action was divided into ten themes for citizens to deliberate upon. Although this participatory event does not necessarily lead to climate action, it led to reflection for future climate action ⁴ .
Brainstorm new ideas	Dedicate public spaces for climate actions	In Vilnius, locals opened a sustainable community-run cafe on municipality land. It became a community centre to share ideas of sustainable living, second-hand markets, and more.
Record citizens' perceptions and suggestions	Website	In Valladolid, the municipality encourages anonymous questions on their website to initiate climate conversations.
Prioritise initiatives	Online applications and municipality website	In Valladolid, citizens can vote on their preferred municipality projects, almost like a version of participatory budget.
Build consensus	Citizen assemblies	In Bologna, the municipality monitored citizen engagement, and found an increase in participation in climate action over the course of citizen assemblies ⁵ . More citizens were inspired to take action themselves, and experts were involved to help citizens with the deliberation process. Several proposals were implemented, and these assemblies started due to citizen protests.
Adjust existing plans	Citizen collectives	Public consultation can be difficult to achieve, but is important. In Nantes, citizens helped re-shape a section of the climate action plan that did not reflect their preferences around the importance of green areas. Nantes organised 80 events for different types of citizen groups and received proposals from over 1000 citizens.

⁴ <https://www.porto.pt/pt/noticia/ciclo-de-conversas-quer-inspirar-e-acelerar-neutralidade-carbonica-na-cidade-ate-2030>

⁵ <https://www.chiara.eco/partecipare/>

The local knowledge possessed by citizens and their experiences can inform policy and advocate local sustainability efforts. Boxes 4 & 5 detail different strategies that can help engage citizens for local climate action.

Box 4. Case Study: Porto Climate Pact

The Porto Local Climate Pact aims to create a diverse community working towards climate neutrality by 2030. It has boosted initiatives taken by both individuals and groups of stakeholders to increase energy efficiency, energy production, and storage, and invest in offsetting actions for the residual emissions. Launched in January 2022, Porto's Climate Pact had already 145 signatories by the end of May 2022.

2030 is the target year for climate neutrality

In 2008, Porto set the objective of cutting 45% of its emissions by 2030. In this view, the local administration is now developing a new SECAP that will aim to achieve an 85% GHG emission reduction and to 15% offsetting target by 2030. The initiative supports the city's ambition by challenging citizens and other organisations to assume leadership of the transition in a collective and participatory manner. Porto focuses on achieving this goal through voluntary and meaningful participation by a broad range of stakeholders to bolster actions at the national and local levels that manage to create a more equal, sustainable and respectful city for all. For example, the municipality is investing in solar panels in numerous buildings across the city, especially schools as well as accelerating the energy transition in municipal housing. This also involves more free public transport, new subway lines, and supporting climate-neutral mobility. The city is also investing in nature-based solutions, like Parque Central de Asprela, or the rehabilitation of water lines.

Recommendations to operationalise this phase:

1. Create mechanisms to:
 - a. Brainstorm **new ideas** with citizens to tackle climate change
 - b. Record citizens' **perceptions and suggestions**
 - c. **Prioritise** climate-change actions thanks to citizens' inputs
 - d. Build **consensus** among citizens, and between citizens and the Municipality actors
 - e. Be flexible so that the Municipality's plans can be **adjusted** based on citizens' inputs
2. Choose the right tool according to the objective:
 - a. **Small-scale events** for deep brainstorming
 - b. **Public debates** (example: citizen assemblies, participatory budget)
 - c. **Online tools** (example: online surveys)
 - d. **Offer resources** such as land for environmental deliberation spaces
3. Work with local vulnerable communities as they have specific needs. For example, in Dublin, the housing crisis has pushed several people to the outskirts of the city, in a deprived area. Locals came up with the idea of greening this neighbourhood, and went door to door engaging others. This resulted in a community conference with 60 people. The Municipality joined the initiative afterwards.

Box 5. European Examples of Collaborative Governance, Participatory Budgets and Citizen Assemblies.**Collaborative Governance through online tools**

In Madrid, an online platform was developed to engage local communities to drive the re-creation of their city. Through the platform, citizens could suggest new ideas and this was used to reduce traffic collaboratively. In Milan, citizen engagement is a key component of climate-neutrality and air-pollution programmes. Milan has developed a community-app which enables citizens to manage shared spaces in newly built housing complexes on previously neglected polluted industrial sites. This programme aims to demonstrate the role of residentially-led experiments in city-wide transformation. The city is also working on behavioural change campaigns using apps, training programs, learning events and serious games to encourage the use of public transport and collect data for climate-resilient policymaking (Climate-KIC., 2020).

Citizens' Assemblies and Peer Parliaments

According to a recent poll, most Europeans recognize the threat of climate change and want to help reduce emissions (EU., 2022). However, despite the overwhelming response, it has been difficult to implement effective climate action strategies. This is usually due to the lack of long-term and effective planning by political representatives. In recent years, citizens have protested this short-sightedness by using participation instruments such as deliberative citizen assemblies (EU., 2022). In EU countries like Denmark, France, Germany, and Ireland, citizens' assemblies have drafted and submitted recommendations to tackle climate change. In Spain, Barcelona has set up climate assemblies for over 100 citizens ranging between 16-75 years, to discuss climate solutions. This engagement builds capacity, fosters ownership of action, and accelerates just decision-making processes. However, managing and running these citizens' assemblies can be difficult as they are expensive, citizens can fatigue or lose interest after some time, and coordinating them is time consuming (EU., 2022). Therefore in 2022, the EU set up deliberative debate to engage citizens in small groups, called Peer Parliaments, across Europe.

Participatory budget:

Several Spanish cities have undertaken citizen engagement initiatives, including the city of Seville, wherein a participatory budget (PB) was created in 2004 to give citizens greater autonomy over the spending of the local government's budget. This PB was half of the council's budget, and citizens voted on the most important sectors (Viable Cities., 2020). The process of PB was highly interactive as it gave citizens the opportunity to discuss the use of local funds and submit proposals. The proposals were discussed in a series of open assemblies. The participants also voted for delegates who would participate in larger district councils, and each district was allowed to submit five proposals to the district council. The final assembly involved the approval of the finalised proposals by the citizens and was key to translating the public's will to policy (Viable Cities., 2020). This process saw the construction of new drainage systems and better pavements, urban renewal programs in poorer areas, and the creation of a community radio-station. This initiative helped democratise public decision-making and representation in Seville.

4. Implementation & collaboration

Goal: empower citizen’s engagement and cooperation to implement actions. The objective is action-focused, involving the implementation of strategies that they defined by themselves in the previous step.

Citizens’ engagement is important in different stages of local climate initiatives ranging from consultation, deliberation and implementation. There are several methods and tools to promote collaborative citizen engagement for local climate action. In Europe and Spain, citizen engagement methods such as collaborative governance, living labs, citizen assemblies and participatory budgets are used for this purpose.

The table 2 gives some examples of local climate change action with citizen engagement:

Table 2. Examples of local climate change action with citizen engagement.

Objective	Actor	Place	Tool	Example
Sustainable consumption	General citizens	Public spaces	Events	In Bilbao, second-hand markets were organised in local festivals to encourage sustainable consumption.
Energy savings	General citizens	Public spaces & library	Communication campaign	In Valencia, energy communities, campaigns, and community spaces have encouraged about 40% energy-office visitors to renovate houses and become energy efficient ⁶ . In Dublin, toolkits were placed in libraries for locals to perform energy audits of their houses ⁷ .
Sustainable mobility	General citizens	Public spaces	Communication campaign	Vilnius declared ‘days without cars’ to encourage the use of bicycles/public transport ⁸ .
Sustainable mobility	General citizens	Public spaces	Change of public spaces use	In Bologna, squares were freed up in front of schools to discourage car use ⁹ .
Sustainable mobility	General citizens	Public spaces	Financial incentives	In Germany, public transport tariffs were reduced for a nation-wide experiment (Loder et al., 2024). Employee benefits from half-day off at work in Mannheim to reduce transport.
Sustainable mobility	Children and parents	Public spaces	Game	School competition in Mannheim incentivised children to walk home from school instead of using their parents’ car.

6 <https://climaienergia.com/es/oficina/energias-renovables/>

7 <https://www.dublincity.ie/library/blog/home-energy-saving-kits-available-all-libraries>

8 <https://madeinvilnius.lt/en/transport/public-transport/day-without-a-car%2C-there-will-be-no-free-public-transport-in-vilnius/>

9 <https://pedestrianspace.org/urban-planning-mobility-in-bologna/>

Waste management	General citizens	Public spaces	Game	Races for garbage picking in Catalonia ¹⁰
Increased knowledge & awareness	Children	Schools	Games	In Bilbao, lego games were organised with children to reimagine their city in a sustainable way ¹¹ .
Increased knowledge and awareness	General citizens	Public areas	Matchmaking	In Australia, citizens were offered opportunities to engage in fieldwork with environmental experts as part of citizen science initiatives.
Regreen the city	General citizens	Private areas	Matchmaking	In Dublin, the 'community roots' app helps match locals wanting to grow food with people with backyard gardens ¹² .

Box 6 presents the details of a citizen engagement initiative for local climate action.

Box 6. European Examples of Citizen Science and Living Labs.

Citizen science has been recognised as a meaningful way to engage citizens with climate efforts (Viable Cities, 2020). For example, the EU SCORE project has worked with citizens in its Coastal City Living Lab regions in Ireland and Italy to deploy 'smart pebbles' (i.e. pebble shaped low-cost sensors that monitor environmental conditions) on local beaches. In both the Italian and Irish cases, school students were engaged in deploying the sensors, as well as monitoring data regularly. This data was then incorporated in the climate models being built by researchers (ATU., 2024). This initiative allowed students to gain awareness about climate change, as well as incorporate locally-generated knowledge within scientific models. The Coastal City Living Lab (CCLL) infrastructure enables effective citizen engagement and stakeholder collaboration, enabling them to co-create and co-design climate strategies, such as ecosystem based adaptation (Tiwari et al., 2022).

¹⁰ <https://ultracleanmarathon.cat/es/>

¹¹ <https://camptecnologico.com/talleres-ninos/>

¹² <https://communityroots.ie/>

Recommendations to operationalize this phase:

1. Define the **main objective(s)** of climate actions, such as:
 - a. Sustainable economic development
 - b. Sustainable mobility
 - c. Improved waste management
 - d. Energy savings
 - e. Increased knowledge and awareness
 - f. Urban regeneration, renaturalization and biodiversity protection
2. Define the **type(s) of actors** that are directly targeted, such as:
 - a. Teachers
 - b. Students
 - c. Children
 - d. Climate change champions or ambassadors
 - e. Workers
3. Define the most suitable place for action, such as:
 - a. Open public spaces
 - b. Living labs
 - c. On-line platforms
 - d. Libraries
 - e. Schools
 - f. Private spaces
3. Define **tool(s)** for action, such as as:
 - a. Communication campaigns
 - b. Festivals
 - c. Grants
 - d. Financial incentives
 - e. Change of public spaces uses
 - f. Games (races for garbage picking in Barcelona, school competition)
 - g. Matchmaking tools

5. Monitoring & Reporting

Goal: citizen engagement is monitored and shared to the Alliance.

The reporting and monitoring of citizen engagements can serve different purposes. It can be used:

- (i) to motivate & inspire citizens to take action,
- (ii) to inform decision-making processes at city, national and European Union levels
- (iii) to advocate for budget allocation. For example, the Department of Citizen Engagement may need to report on impacts to negotiate their operational budget.

Depending on the priority objective(s), reporting can focus on quantitative, qualitative data, or mix of both through use of different tools:

- *Reporting* can focus on *individual actions* such as mobility decisions and collective actions such as creating a community garden. As an *example of purely quantitative and individual-based reporting*, some cities (Vilnius) and countries (Germany) include climate-change-related questions in national or city census to inform decision-making and advocate for budget allocation. The census then provides quantitative data.
- *Storytelling* of successful citizen engagement initiatives is a *qualitative methodology* that can be applied to both individual and collective levels. It can be used to motivate and inspire citizens, and to inform decision-makers by drawing learnings from specific initiatives. This approach is used in Lyon for example.
- Other reporting tools include the *use of websites and smartphone applications*. The city of Nantes developed an app with mini-challenges for citizens, such as eating only vegetarian food for a week. Challenges are done as a team, which are created based on geographical proximity and common interests (food, transport, etc). Once the challenge is completed, the user sees how much CO₂ (s)he has saved during this week, with an estimation of yearly carbon saving if the person would continue those practices throughout the year. The objective of the app is both to report individual efforts but also to motivate people to act, thanks to a playful App design. Nonetheless, self-reported data may be inaccurate, which can hinder the credibility of municipalities. Automatised tools, such as smart metres are found to be more accurate but they may cause confidentiality issues. *Installation of sensors to measure bike-lane traffic* and the *creation of maps* with existing citizen initiatives are examples of additional tools which can inspire citizens, inform decision-makers and be used for advocacy purposes thanks to easily accessible data.
- In our workshop, although most cities mentioned a lack of monitoring of relevant data, some cities like Bologna also mentioned meaningful examples. For instance, the local municipality found permanent changes in citizens' behaviour stemming from weekly 'no car days' in the main town area. Additionally, *citizen science activities* can also aid with monitoring of data, and allow citizens to co-produce scientific knowledge. However, it is worth noting that most cities have struggled to effectively monitor data, due to lack of resources, funding, and skills within municipalities; lack of awareness and understanding of the importance of monitoring and its contribution to policy; lack of prioritisation due to greater focus on conception/implementation of initiatives; and limited reliable and cost-effective monitoring tools and technology.

Table 3 provides a summary of monitoring tools:

Table 3. Summary of monitoring tools

	Type of data	Focus on individual or collective actions?	Main monitoring objective
National or city census	Quantitative	Collective	Inform decision-making processes Advocate for budget allocation
Storytelling	Qualitative	Individual and collective	Motivate and inspire citizens
Best practices map	Qualitative	Individual and collective	Motivate and inspire citizens
Smart-phone game applications	Quantitative	Individual	Motivate and inspire citizens
Sensors, smart metres	Quantitative	Individual	Inform decision-making processes Advocate for budget allocation

Recommendations to operationalize this phase:

- Define the **objective and audience** of monitoring and reporting.
- Develop **online platforms displaying the citizens' initiatives**. A map or interactive tool could be useful for people to see what is happening close to them.
- Promote **reflection** on climate action, challenges, and possibilities using **urban pedagogy** tools in formal and informal settings.
- Discuss the **joint contributions** of the municipality and citizens in a broader framework, highlighting the needs for climate justice and the responsibilities of other actors, other levels of governments and companies.
- Beware that monitoring should **not be used as controlling**, as this would discourage voluntary citizens' engagement!

Conclusion

Effective citizen participation is essential for the successful design and implementation of climate strategies in cities. To facilitate such participation, this guide proposes a five-phase process: (1) citizens first discover the climate strategy, (2) then decide to join it, (3) followed by choosing specific climate targets and defining how to achieve them, (4) implementing the actions, and (5) finally monitoring and reporting on activities. Together, these phases involve a process of learning and social empowerment.

The first step relates to the “**discovery**” of the city’s objectives. At this stage, citizens and other local actors can understand the scientific necessity and the relevance of the city’s emissions target as a contribution to a global objective.

The second step sees the **entry** of the citizen’s participation into the city’s action. The means and individuals used to introduce the city’s plans are key to receive the trust necessary for citizens to become participants. Meeting people in day-to-day spaces of encounter (e.g. parks), and for playful activities help building proximity and trust. Based on the Motivation-Capacity-Ownership framework, we provide a list of suggestions to promote an inclusive citizen engagement for the Climate Mission Alliance 2030. The motivation of citizens is linked to the expected co-benefits of climate action with a focus on returns of investment and through positive narratives. To build citizens’ capacity, local associations help create social networks and adapt the strategies according to the vulnerabilities and needs of different groups. To promote ownership, the long-term involvement of actors and of the initiatives is important to the trust in the municipality.

The third step is to get citizens, together with the Municipality, **defining what to do and how**. This step implies choosing specific climate targets and defining how to achieve them, resulting in concrete **commitments** from the city and citizens. To create a common understanding and a sense of shared responsibility on local climate change action, participatory and deliberative processes should be utilised, paying attention to special needs and vulnerabilities. Citizens are more prone to disengage when they do not see the outcome of the initiative they were involved in, therefore it is key to set realistic goals.

The fourth step is **implementation** and greatly relies on the coherence of the decisions made in the previous steps. The objectives must be well tailored to the citizen’s individual and collective motivation and capacities, as well as the tools used.

The fifth **monitoring** step also needs to be adaptive as it requires additional participation from citizens to be representative. Establishing proximity with the citizen, through physical or virtual spaces, contributes to gather their feedback. Storytelling exercises can help understand their motivations and capacities.

Overall, a successful citizen participation should build upon the existing local social capital. Climate change opportunities should be linked to the activities and mission of existing organisations and networks. The motivations and limitations of the citizens and association can be managed but need to be understood and acknowledged. Building trust is key to ensure long-term and growing participation. Beyond their own actions, the municipality and its citizens can highlight their needs for support and justice from other actors, including other levels of governments and the private sectors. In its role as orchestrator, the city must focus on the existing potential, including the networks and groups that already express the needs and aspirations of citizens in Valencia.

Figure 5. Examples of best practices used for citizen engagement across Europe. The numbers correspond to the steps of citizen engagement for which each kind of practices might be more suitable.

Conclusión (en español)

La participación ciudadana efectiva es esencial para el éxito del diseño y la aplicación de estrategias climáticas en las ciudades. Para facilitar dicha participación, esta guía propone un proceso de cinco fases: (1) la ciudadanía descubre la estrategia climática, (2) toma la decisión de sumarse a ella, (3) a continuación se definen objetivos climáticos específicos y cómo alcanzarlos (4) se ejecutan las acciones planteadas en la fase anterior y (5) por último se monitorean y se reportan las actividades. En conjunto, las cinco fases implican un proceso de aprendizaje y empoderamiento social.

El primer paso se refiere al “**descubrimiento**” del objetivo de la ciudad. En esta fase, los ciudadanos y otros agentes locales pueden comprender la necesidad científica y la relevancia de la meta de emisiones de la ciudad como contribución a un objetivo global.

En la segunda etapa se produce la **entrada** de la ciudadanía en la acción climática. Los medios de difusión y las personas que divulgan el plan climático de la ciudad son clave para obtener la confianza necesaria y los ciudadanos se convierten en participantes. Reunirse con la gente en espacios cotidianos de encuentro (por ejemplo, parques) y realizar actividades lúdicas ayuda a crear proximidad y confianza. Basándonos en el marco Motivación-Capacidad-Apropiación, ofrecemos una lista de sugerencias para promover una participación ciudadana inclusiva en la Alianza para la Misión Climática 2030. La motivación de los ciudadanos está vinculada a los co-beneficios esperados de la acción climática, por lo que es importante enfatizar el rendimiento de las inversiones e implementar narrativas positivas. Las asociaciones locales juegan un rol clave en la creación de redes y en la adaptación de las estrategias según las vulnerabilidades y necesidades de los distintos grupos,

lo cual fortalece las capacidades de la ciudadanía. Para promover la apropiación y la confianza en el Municipio, la participación a largo plazo de los actores y de las iniciativas es crucial.

El tercer paso es conseguir que los ciudadanos, junto con el Ayuntamiento, **definan qué hacer y cómo**. Este paso implica elegir objetivos climáticos específicos y definir cómo alcanzarlos, lo que se traduce en **compromisos** concretos por parte de la ciudad y de los ciudadanos. Para crear un entendimiento común y un sentido de responsabilidad compartida en la acción local contra el cambio climático, deben utilizarse procesos participativos y deliberativos, prestando atención a las necesidades y vulnerabilidades especiales. Los ciudadanos son más propensos a desvincularse cuando no ven el resultado de la iniciativa en la que han participado.

El cuarto paso es la **implementación**, la cual depende en gran medida de la coherencia de las decisiones tomadas en los pasos anteriores. Los objetivos deben estar bien adaptados a las motivaciones y capacidades individuales y colectivas de los ciudadanos, así como a las herramientas utilizadas.

El quinto paso es el **seguimiento**, el cual también debe ser adaptativo, ya que requiere una participación adicional de los ciudadanos para ser representativo. El uso de espacios de acercamiento tanto físicos como virtuales y la apertura a diversas formas de información, como la narración de historias, pueden ayudar a captar los resultados de la participación ciudadana, a la luz de sus motivaciones y capacidades.

Con un enfoque ampliado a través de las cinco fases, una participación ciudadana efectiva debe basarse en el capital social local existente. Las oportunidades del cambio climático deben vincularse a las actividades y la misión de las organizaciones y redes existentes. Las motivaciones y limitaciones de los ciudadanos y las organizaciones pueden gestionarse, pero es necesario comprenderlas y reconocerlas. Además de sus propias acciones, el municipio y sus habitantes pueden resaltar cuáles son sus necesidades de apoyo y de justicia social por parte de otros actores, incluidos otros niveles de gobierno y los sectores privados. Generar confianza es clave para garantizar una participación creciente y sostenida en el tiempo. En su papel de orquestadora, la ciudad debe centrarse en el potencial existente, incluidas las redes y grupos que ya expresan las necesidades y aspiraciones de la población de Valencia.

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